
Role of Technology in Accounting Field

Prof. Mrs. Ulka Mansing Gharge

Yashwantrao Chavan Mahavidyalay, Islampur.

Corresponding Author – Prof. Mrs. Ulka Mansing Gharge

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15067222

Introduction:

Accounting is an art of recording, classifying, and summarizing business transactions in a significant manner. Accounting technology in the form of tools, software, and systems plays a vital role in the accounting field. Accounting technology has changed how accounting is done, moving from a manual, paper-based process to digital workflows. Tasks that take weeks can now be completed in minutes. Accounting technology acts as a catalyst, increasing efficiency, enhancing accuracy, and saving time for accounting teams across all industries. Automation reduces manual errors and saves time. Advanced security measures protect sensitive information. A significant technological revolution has affected various aspects of business operations, including accounting.

Objective of the Study:

1. To study various technologies used in the accounting field.
2. To study the effects of technology on the working of the accounting field.

Methods of Data Collection:

For the present study, secondary sources of data collection like books, magazines, and websites are used.

Major Technologies that play a pivotal role in Accounting:

Automation and Artificial Intelligence (AI):

Tasks that were repetitive, labor-intensive, and time-consuming, such as audit, tax preparation, payroll, and banking transactions, are now efficiently handled through AI and automation. This enables accountants to concentrate on more complex tasks such as financial analysis and strategic planning. Automated systems reduce the risk of human error, which results in more accurate financial reporting, data entry, account reconciliations, and report generation. AI transforms accounting processes, including handling routine tasks, minimizing human errors, and enhancing the accuracy of business transactions and financial statements. AI enables detailed analysis of extensive data in a shorter time, detecting risks overlooked in traditional auditing. AI enables the detection of fraud, risk assessment, and data analysis.

Machine Learning (ML):

Machine learning utilizes algorithms to create models that process extensive data sets. Machine learning in accounting handles vast data sets, which are laborious for human analysis. Advanced machine learning models contribute to accuracy and fraud prevention in modern accounting. Machine learning can automate repetitive tasks such as data entry and reconciliation. It helps detect and prevent

fraud. Machine learning is very relevant for the fields of accounting and finance. Machine learning sees patterns that human could never see. Machine learning can solve accounting problems like data entry, bank reconciliation and invoice processing. Machine learning for accounting can improve efficiency and accuracy, saving your precious time and headaches. Although there are several benefits of machine learning, it has challenges also. Technology can miss something that a human would catch. Machine learning can solve accounting problems like data entry, Bank reconciliation and invoice processing. Accountants can use machine learning to streamline tasks, catch errors, and reduce operational costs.

Cloud based accounting:

In modern accounting, the storing data in a centralized location accessible via internet. This centralized storage encourages teamwork, continuous updates, empower clients and accountants to make accurate decisions while workflow automation save time and enhance accessibility and security. Transforming manual financial tracking into computerized systems. Real time financial reporting possible allowing businesses to take decisions on the latest information

Robotic process automation (RPA):

This software driven solution enables execution of routine accounting processes without requiring human intervention. Accountants uses Robotic process automation for atomic invoice processing, identifying discrepancies in financial records, addressing vendor inquiries. It reduces the time spent on repetitive tasks, reducing the risks of human errors. Robotic process automation cuts down processing time, allowing accountants and financial experts focus on more value added tasks such as detailed data analysis and report preparation. Robotic accounting is artificial intelligence that provides helping

hand to finance department Robotic accounting software run across any and every accounting platform a business uses. The future of Robotic process automation looks bright as organization continue to adopt automation to remain competitive. This automation drastically reduces the time and cost associated with manual processing. Robotic process automation systems are flexible and can be adjusted according to business needs.

Block Chain:

Block Chain Accounting provides full transparency Accountant, auditor and client can access an identical ledger to verify the information on it. Record stored on the block chain are permanent and transparent. The Information cannot be erased. Unlike a traditional ledger, block chain is not owned by a single person or organization instead of the ledger exist across multiple computers, cannot be controlled by a single entity. The use of cryptographic keys, which lock and unlock data helps to keep block chain records safe and secure. Storing financial data safety and securely has always been of vital importance in the Accounting industry. With layers of encryption and cryptographic keys, block chains offer a high security. Once transactor on the block chain, transactions cannot be altered or removed which means auditors can trace them back.

Big Data:

It allows collection and analysis of vast financial data from various sources. This helps Accountants to gain deeper insights into a company's financial performance. They can identify trends, patterns that might go unnoticed with traditional methods. Earlier, manual data recording methods limited the visibility of data. Rise of technology and big data in Accounting has revolutionized how auditing is done. Big data analysis is a most powerfully tool in detecting and preventing financial fraud. Using big data analytics tools allows to process data faster and

reduce costs, save time and increase overall efficiency. Big data is used in machine learning, predictive, modeling and other advanced analytics to solve business problems and make informed decisions.

Impact of Modern Technology on Accounting:

Technology has basically changed the accounting field. This technological advancement is both an asset and as liability for the company's accountant. Technology has produced three effects on accounting positive, negative and neutral. Each effect requires accounting profession to adopt to the new reality.

Positive impacts of technology on Accounting:

- **Improved Accuracy:** Computer system reduce errors and offer reliable financial information with minimizing the risk of human mistakes. Information Technology significantly impacted the field of accounting also how tasks are performed and managed.
- **Increased efficiency:** Technology allows accountants to access information and automatically update records as transactions happens.
- **Faster processing:** Technology helps accountants to speedily generate reports for quick management decision making.
- **Better Collaboration:** Technology helps accountants to collaborate more easily with other stakeholders.
- **Reduced repetitive tasks:** Technology allows accountant to spend less time on repetitive work, such as manual data entry.
- **Improved decision making:** Technology allows accountants to find financial documents, collect information and evaluate the effect on financial decisions.
- **Enhance Accounting Accuracy:** Accounting Software allows for the quick creation of countless entries in

the ledger with little chance of data manipulation. Software prepares all the necessary reports as compare to traditional manual accounting system; it prepares manual reports, increasing chance of making errors, takes lot of time.

- **Minimize Frauds:** Accounting work made via computers reduces human involvement and thus frauds. Data visualization aids in identifying sings of dishonest behavior in transactions whereas data mining is applied in identifying red flags of acquisition fraud and misleading data.
- **Auditing:** Technology provides relevant information for internal as well as external audit. Auditors utilize the data techniques used in risk assessment and controls testing, to arrive at decisions and judgement. The level of accuracy and efficiency of audits are currently being redefined by automated devices.

Negative Impacts of Technology on Accounting :

The Acceptance of modern technology in the accounting sector has improved several works in accounting but at the same time, use of Advanced technology has some demerits also----

- **Redundancy of previous technologies:** The outdated accounting technology making it challenging to keep using them. To keep with updated latest technology results in additional expenses which leads to reduce profitability of an organization.
- **Limitations on Automation:** Automation allows transfer of data in the form of payments and invoices automatically too many users simultaneously. It reduces time, if data is incorrect at one level; the errors build up in the following level.
- **Security Threats:** Accounting technology store the data and information in the electronic form, which is convenient to store and

retrieve. On the contrary accounting system may hack by cybercriminals if the networks safety measures are not allowed properly which results in leakage of sensitive financial data and trade secrets. Also risk of unlawful access accounting access accounting information during information exchange.

- **Impact on accounting jobs:** Accepting modern technologies in accounting has totally transferred the accounting tasks. Work at entry level accounting like purchasing billing, order entry, reporting on costs, accounts payable and accounts receivable are automated. This result in the reduced demand for fresh manpower. At present, nearly 60 % of the service that accountants and other professionals perform can be automated using the available technology.

Conclusion of the Study:

Innovations will change how accountants work but technology cannot replace human judgement, strategic advice, relationships. Education and ethics will continue to be vital in the industry. Change will requiring accountants to continuously learn and adopt to new tools and regulations. As systems become more intelligent and automated, accountant's responsibilities will broaden. As technology Advances, accounting will become more engaging, dynamic and vital to business strategy. Accountants, who use

new tools, seek self-improvement and stay agile will find many opportunities ahead.

Suggestions of the Study:

As per necessity and requirements, technology should used. Be careful while using modern technology. Proper security measures should take into account.

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